

Sensor less speed estimation Technique for the Vector Controlled Permanent Magnet Synchronous Motor Drive

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Abstract

In recent years, much endeavor has been made to improve the performance of speed sensor less permanent magnet synchronous motor drives, especially at low speeds by, identifying stator resistance together with speed. Model-based speed and stator resistance estimators are the most common schemes used in the literature. There are several other methods for estimating the rotor speed and stator resistance. One popular method among them is Model Reference Adaptive System (MRAS). This work corresponds to estimating the speed and stator resistance using active and reactive power based MRAS. Several speed estimation methods for sensor less PMSM drives have been proposed. Performance of them is not satisfactory at low speed. When the stator resistance value in the speed estimator is incorrect, the estimator does not work satisfactorily. The stator resistance varies with the temperature of the machine, so it should be estimated adaptively. Due to the high efficiency and good controllability, PMSM drives are largely used in many industrial applications. At the present classic PID controller is mostly used, whose performance is affected dramatically by parameters of motor. In addition, in order to reduce cost and avoid the limitation of mechanical sensor. People proposed sensor less techniques which are arousing great interest. They aim at eliminating mechanical sensor, which are rather expensive and delicate, especially if accurate mounting and calibration are necessary, and at obtaining rotor position and angular velocity from the measurement of only electrical quantities. But the precision of position estimation often depends on motor's parameters. Naturally, the precise determination of PMSM parameters is of great significance.

Much identification of the motor's parameters is proposed to increase the performance of controllers and precision of position estimation. To control PMSM position and speed sensors are indispensable because, the current should be controlled depending on the rotor position. The vector control drive provides wide range of speeds, high torque capability and high efficiency. Also the vector control of PM motors is much simpler than of induction motors because there is no need to consider the slip frequency as in the induction motor drive. Conventional vector control of PM motor requires a motor position sensor to correctly orient the current vector orthogonally to the flux, because the rotor flux is obtained from the permanent magnets. It is possible to control the torque by acting simply on the amplitude of the stator current. Thus we can achieve a high degree of torque control over a wide speed range including the standstill can be achieved. Because there is no need to consider the slip frequency as in the induction motor drives. Conventional vector control of PM motor requires a motor position sensor to correctly orient the current vector orthogonally to the flux, because the rotor flux is obtained from the permanent magnets. It is possible to control the torque by acting simply on the amplitude of the stator current. Thus we can achieve a high degree of torque control over a wide speed range including the standstill can be achieved.

Keywords: model reference adaptive system, reactive power speed estimation, vector control permanent magnet synchronous motor.

1. Introduction

This report presents a parameter estimation technique for the permanent magnet synchronous motor drive. A model reference adaptive system (MRAS) has been formed by using the